

IMI2 821520 – ConcePTION
ConcePTION
WP7 – Information and data governance, ethics, technology and data catalogue and quality support

D7.19 Report providing the details on the informed consent procedures, informed consent sheets and information sheets for demonstration studies in WP2 & 5. IRB approval procedures and confirmation for WP2 demonstration studies and WP5 outreach.

Lead contributor	Constanza Andaur Navarro (1 - UMCU) c.l.andaurnavarro@umcutrecht.nl
Other contributors	Miriam Sturkenboom (1 - UMCU) Rebecca Bromley (28 - UMAN) Miranda van Tuyl (9 - LAREB) Stephanie Tcherny-Lessenlot (39 - SANOFI)

Document history

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Abstract

Started in 2019, the ConcePTION project aims to establish a large ecosystem to provide fast and reliable evidence on drug safety during pregnancy and breastfeeding. ConcePTION partners are conducting studies across Europe, some of them with the close collaboration of pregnant and breastfeeding women, which is one of the cornerstones of the project.

As described in the research proposal, certain tasks in work packages 2 and 5 involve approaching pregnant and breastfeeding women to explore their needs regarding drug safety information. In this report on deliverable D7.19, we describe the collection and public availability of the ethical documentation for work package 2 and 5.

Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
WP	Work Package
DoA	Description of Action
REC	regional ethics committee
HCP	Health Care Providers
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment

Purpose and scope of this document

One of the purposes of WP7 in the ConcePTION project is to provide ethical, governance, and quality assessment support for the conduct of distributed data collection and analyses which supports the generation of high quality real world evidence. Task 7.10 involves collecting copies from all templates, Institutional Review Board (IRB) comments and approvals, and documentation from the sites that are required to comply with the ethical and IMI obligations.

The purpose of deliverable D7.19 is to describe the collection of ethical documentation of the activities carried out within work package 2 and 5 (WP2, WP5) that involves prospective primary data collection within the ConcePTION project, with the aim to demonstrate how studies comply with current ethical and local governance requirements when gathering prospective data from pregnant and breastfeeding women.

From the ConcePTION Description of Action (DoA), D7.19 description is:

“Report providing the details on the informed consent procedures, informed consent sheets and information sheets for demonstration studies in WP2 & 5. IRB approval procedures and confirmation for WP2 demonstration studies and WP5 outreach”

Background

ConcePTION aims to create an ecosystem for the rapid and robust generation of evidence on the safety of medications in pregnancy and lactation, using both existing and newly generated real-world data. The present report is one of the five deliverables in task 7.10 and involves our partners from WP2 and WP5.

Task 7.10 of WP7 is describe as follow in the ConcePTION Description of Action (DoA):

“In this task we will collect copies from all templates, IRB review comments and approvals and documentation from the sites that are required to comply with the ethical (see section 5) and IMI obligations. This task will deliverable five deliverables (D7.18-7.22), providing proof and documentation that ConcePTION partners and third parties are compliant.”

WP2 focusses on the collection and analysis of reported pregnancies (exposed and non-exposed) as well as primary data collection on neurodevelopmental outcomes. In particular, task 2.5 within WP2 comprises five demonstration projects. WP5

Work Package 2

The objective of WP2 is to optimize pharmacovigilance data collection on reported pregnancies and data sharing plus analytical methodologies to quantify and characterize risks associated with use of medications during pregnancy and lactation rapidly and efficiently. Prospective primary data collection is performed in some of the demonstration projects within WP2.

Briefly, task 2.5 in WP2 comprises five demonstration projects listed below:

1. *Analysis of existing pregnancy pharmacovigilance and active surveillance data*
2. *Database of prospective pregnancy exposure and outcome data*
3. *LIFETIME: Long-term health and development following In-utero Foetal Exposure to Medications*
4. *Delineating the full teratogenic phenotype of a newly identified teratogen e.g., mycophenolic acid (mycophenolate mofetil (MMF), mycophenolate sodium)*
5. *Cross-validation of self-reported exposure and outcome data*

Demonstration project 1 does not perform primary data collection and therefore, it has been excluded from this report.

Work Package 5

The aim of WP5 is to improve the value, quality, and harmonization of the dissemination of information on the available evidence related to medicine use in pregnancy and the potential effects on the mother, embryos, and fetus before and during pregnancy as well as to infants during breastfeeding.

In particular sub-task 5.1.3 aimed to explore pregnant and breastfeeding women’s and healthcare professionals’ (HCPs) information needs regarding the safety of drugs in pregnancy or during breastfeeding, and preferences for receiving such information in the future, both regarding content of the information and how it is delivered/made accessible to them in a knowledge bank. The methods deployed included anonymous online surveys and focus group with HCPs and pregnant or breastfeeding women. Consequently, consented, and anonymized data is collected. For other task and sub-task within WP5 (i.e., e-learning platform and knowledge bank), the scope of this delivery is not applicable.

Task description

This deliverable report is based on the collection of ethical documentation, that is – templates, informed consent procedures, informed consent sheets, participant's information sheets, and Data Management Plan (DMP) and Data Impact Protection Assessment (DPIA), if applicable. The aim is to provide proof and public documentation that ConcePTION partners and third parties are compliant their ethical and local governance requirement.

The scope of this particular delivery is ethical and governance documentation related to studies in which prospective primary data collection is performed with consent of the participants. It is not part of this deliverable to monitor or audit whether information provision, consent procedures, and ethical approvals were conducted according to national/regional guidelines or local requirements where the studies will take place or whether they followed the recommendation from the ConcePTION consortium ([Singleton & Cunnington 2020](#)).

From September 2022 to September 2023, we approached WP and DP leads via e-mail requesting the aforementioned documentation from. [Table 1](#) and [Table 2](#) show the studies, the documentation shared, name of the files in the IMI-ConcePTION Member Area, and the contact person who handled the documentation till the moment of the submission of the present report for WP2 and WP5, respectively. We expect partners to still contribute to this 'live' report with further documentation once they received approvals by uploading files in the corresponding WP folder in the IMI-ConcePTION Member Area.

Table 1. Ethical documentation for WP2

STUDY	DOCUMENTATION SHARED WITH WP7	NAME OF THE FILE IN IMI-CONCEPTION MEMBER AREA	CONTACT PERSON IN WP2
Demo Project 2: Database of prospective pregnancy exposure and outcome data	○ REC approval	Please address contact person.	Ursula Winterfeld Ursula.Winterfeld[at]chuv[dot]ch
Demo Project 3: LIFETiME: Long-term health and development following In-utero Foetal Exposure to Medications	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DMP <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Protocol <input type="checkbox"/> Informed consent <input type="checkbox"/> Information sheet <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> REC approval	Child_neurodevelopment_following_prenatal_exposure_to_anti_seizure_medications-_a_pilot_extension_to_.pdf UK EPR Extension PILOT PROTOCOL Version 1 09.09.2022 IRAS 298187_Letter_of_HRA_Approval 19 06 2023.pdf 298187 Favourable_opinion_on_further_information 16.05.23[40]	Rebecca Bromley rebecca.bromley[at]manchester.ac[dot]uk
Demo Project 4: Delineating the full teratogenic phenotype of a newly identified teratogen e.g., mycophenolic acid (mycophenolate mofetil (MMF), mycophenolate sodium).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DMP <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Protocol <input type="checkbox"/> Informed consent <input type="checkbox"/> Information sheet <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> REC approval	Data Management Plan FES Version 1 21.04.2023.pdf Fetal Exposure Study PROTOCOL Version 2 13.07.2023 .pdf 327640_(Approval)_Letter_of_HRA_Approval 08 08 2023.pdf 23.LO.0599. IRAS 327640.FIFO Letter with recommendation 08.08.23 (1).pdf	Rebecca Bromley rebecca.bromley[at]manchester.ac[dot]uk
Demo Project 5: Cross-validation of self-reported exposure and outcome data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DMP <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Protocol <input type="checkbox"/> Informed consent <input type="checkbox"/> Information sheet <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> REC approval	Data Management Plan FES Version 1 21.04.2023.pdf Fetal Exposure Study PROTOCOL Version 2 13.07.2023 .pdf 327640_(Approval)_Letter_of_HRA_Approval 08 08 2023.pdf 23.LO.0599. IRAS 327640.FIFO Letter with recommendation 08.08.23 (1).pdf	Rebecca Bromley rebecca.bromley[at]manchester.ac[dot]uk

○ Available but contact lead of demonstration project for further information on this document.
 Available in the IMI-ConcePTION Member Area

Table 2. Ethical documentation for WP5

STUDY	DOCUMENTATION SHARED WITH WP7	NAME OF THE FILE IN IMI-CONCEPTION MEMBER AREA	CONTACT PERSON IN WP5
Sub-task 5.1.3: Pregnant and breastfeeding women's and healthcare professionals' information needs regarding drug use during pregnancy and lactation	<input type="radio"/> Templates <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> IRB approval	Niet WMO verklaring focurgroep onderzoek.pdf	Leàn Rolfes l.rolfes[at]lareb[dot]nl

Available but contact lead of demonstration project for further information.

Available in the IMI-ConcePTION Member Area

Repository structure and availability

We proposed to make the documentation available via the [IMI-ConcePTION Member Area](#) to allow related WP leads/members to upload their documentation after the date of submission of this deliverable, if deemed necessary. Each WP has been assigned a folder in the IMI-ConcePTION Member Area where they can store related documentation (Figure 1). In the case of WP4, they will need to create a folder named 'Ethics deliveries' where to store the related documentation.

The present report will be made available as 'Files' in the public repository ([Zenodo – IMI ConcePTION](#)), after approval of this report. The report will be in the public domain, and available for download.

Figure 1. Example of repository for related documentation in the IMI-ConcePTION Member Area

Documents

The screenshot displays the IMI-ConcePTION Member Area interface. On the left, a tree view shows the folder structure under 'Work package 3', including '0- WP3 Management Meeting', '1- WP3 Meetings', '2- Ethics Deliverables', and 'In vivo studies'. The 'In vivo studies' folder is selected, and its contents are shown in a table on the right. The table has columns for 'Name', 'Date modified', and 'Size'. Three PDF files are listed:

Name	Date modified	Size
3b- AutRigMinistero[1181]Approvazione_Notifica_BDN_Forni_1181.pdf	11/10/2022 3:35 PM	454.2 KB
3c- AutRigMinistero [1185]Autorizzazione_202132_Bacci_1185.pdf new.pdf	11/10/2022 3:57 PM	162.7 KB
AutRigMinistero[1282]Autorizzazione_202335_Bacci_1282.pdf	8/11/2023 5:05 PM	789.0 KB

At the bottom of the interface, there is a search bar, a 'Views' section with icons for grid, list, and refresh, an 'Actions' section with icons for download, share, and print, and a footer showing 'Items per Page: 10' and '3 Items'.

Conclusion

The present Report provides an overview of the ethical documentation related to primary data collection within WP2 and WP5. Until the submission of this deliverable, only WP5 has provided the documentation regarding sub-task 5.1.3 through the IMI-ConcePTION Member Area. We expect further ethical documentation to be made available through the same media after the approval of this deliverable.

References

Singleton, P., & Cunnington, M. (2020). Report on initial information and research governance for WP1-5 (D7.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5840292>